

Estimating the scale and distribution of Female Genital Mutilation / Cutting in global migrant populations.

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Abstract

This analysis suggests that 7.3-million of the 130-million global female migrant population is potentially impacted by FGM/C, with more than half of them originating from just four countries of origin: Egypt, Indonesia, Somalia, and Sudan. This analysis shows that the country-of-residence of impacted migrant population skews heavily towards Africa, the Middle East and Asia, where FGM/C is already known to be practised by indigenous populations. Migration patterns within and between Africa, the Middle East, and Asia suggest that the potential for onward migration must be considered when applying the Extrapolation-of-FGM/C-Countries'-Prevalence-Data method to countries where the practice is almost exclusively found within the migrant population – such as in Europe and the United States. This calls for a more profound analysis of ethnic and ancestral origins than simply considering a migrants' country of birth, as is often the case, when assessing risk.

1. A global practice

The practice of Female Genital Mutilation / Cutting (FGM/C) is defined by the World Health Organisation as the ‘partial or total removal of external female genitalia or other injury to the female genital organs for non-medical reasons’ (WHO, 2020). While the practice has been documented in numerous global cultures and contexts (Equality Now et al., 2020), most survivors are African (UNICEF, 2022). Each year some three million more girls are at risk – almost all cut before the age of 15 (WHO, 2020), with some cut within a few weeks of birth (e.g. Nigeria, Indonesia), others as young children (e.g. Somalia, Egypt), while still others undergo FGM/C as teenagers (Kenya, Tanzania) (28 Too Many, 2021). In 2016, UNICEF estimated that 200 million women and girls from thirty countries were impacted by FGM/C (UNICEF, 2016), yet evidence suggests that the practice is prevalent in indigenous and migrant populations in at least ninety-two countries (Equality Now, End FGM European Network & End FGM/C US Network, 2020). While the quality of prevalence data varies across these countries, this data provides a clear indication that the impacted population is larger and more diverse than that referenced by UNICEF. Prevalence across these ninety-two countries ranges from as high as 99% in Somalia to less than 1% in Cameroon, Uganda, and Zambia (28 Too Many, 2021). Since population sizes in countries of practice vary dramatically, impacted populations are geographically concentrated, with Indonesia, Egypt, and Ethiopia accounting for more than half the UNICEF estimate (UNICEF, 2016). While prevalence rates are dropping in many countries, population growth is often outpacing prevalence gains, resulting in a net increase in the number of girls at risk (UNICEF, 2014).

2. A transnational practice

This paper places the author's PhD research – focused on FGM/C within migrant populations resident in the United States – within the broader context of the distribution of FGM/C in migrant populations globally. With a global female migrant population estimated at just over 130 million (UNPD, 2019a) this analysis suggests that over 7.3 million of those migrant women and girls are potentially impacted by FGM/C, with more than half of them originating from just four countries of origin: Egypt, Indonesia, Somalia, and Sudan. While most experienced FGM/C while still resident in their countries of origin prior to migration, much less is known about the ongoing risk to their daughters in their countries of residence. This scene-setting analysis helps to contextualise FGM/C in the United States, where over half a million migrants impacted by FGM/C are estimated to be resident (Goldberg et al., 2016), in light of the scale and distribution of the practice within migrant populations across the rest of the world.

3. Methodology

Typically, three methods are deployed to estimate the scale of FGM/C in a population: population surveys, direct incident reports, and The Extrapolation of FGM/C Countries' Prevalence Data method (De Schrijver et al., 2020). The first and most expensive of these, population surveys, is the method of choice in countries of origin where large scale household surveys are conducted every five-years. These population surveys in countries of origin provided a critical input variable to this research.

The second method, direct incident reports (including crime and medical data), are relied on and even mandated in some jurisdictions (Home Office, UK Government, 2015).

However these reports often underestimate the true extent of the practice, resulting in a large dark figure (Malik *et al.*, 2018).

The third and most widely used process for estimating the scale and distribution of the FGM/C impacted population in migrant populations is the Extrapolation of FGM/C Countries' Prevalence Data method (De Schrijver *et al.*, 2020). While there is a clear refinement of the method evident in the literature, at its core, the Extrapolation of FGM/C Countries' Prevalence Data method relies on three variables:

1. the prevalence rate in the country of origin,
2. the migrant population in the country under examination,
3. an estimation of the impact of migration and acculturation on prevalence.

This method, which extrapolates prevalence from countries of origin to populations living in the diaspora, is often deployed in a purely quantitative fashion based on secondary data, with very little attention given to the qualitative aspects originally designed into the mix-method approach (EIGE and ICF Consulting Ltd, 2018). The first two variables – population and prevalence – constitute the quantitative components of the method. The third variable, the impact of migration and acculturation on prevalence, calls for a mix-method approach. While the authors larger study in the United States deploys this mix-method approach, the scope of this paper required a more limited approach based only on secondary data.

4. Data sources

Equality Now *et al.* (2020) segmented the countries where FGM/C is known to be practised by the quality of prevalence data available as follows:

- a. those with '*national representative surveys*' of FGM/C prevalence – mainly in Africa (n=32);
- b. those with '*indirect estimates*' of FGM/C prevalence – mainly migrant populations in the global North (n=31);
- c. those with '*small-scale studies*' of FGM/C prevalence – mainly in Asia and the Middle East (n=15);
- d. those with '*anecdotal evidence*' of FGM/C (n=15).

This study excluded thirty-one countries where FGM/C was exclusively evident within the migrant population and fifteen countries with limited anecdotal evidence. National average FGM/C prevalence estimates were collated for thirty-six of the forty-seven countries of origin, where national prevalence exceeded 0.5% and the practice was not isolated within an insignificantly small pocket of the population (such as is the case in India, Pakistan, and the Russian Federation). The resultant prevalence data (Table 1) was based on the latest available Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS), Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) or national statistical bureau data (in the case of Indonesia and Somalia) and supplemented by calculations for those countries that did not have national survey data available, notably:

Kuwait (Chibber, El-saleh and Harmi, 2011)

Malaysia (Ainslie, 2015; Dahlui, 2012; Ibrahim and Tegal, 2019; Isa et al., 1999; Khan, 2010; Marranci, 2015; Merli, 2010; Rashid and Iguchi, 2019)

Saudi Arabia (Milaat et al., 2018; Rouzi et al., 2019)

United Arab Emirates (Al Awar et al., 2020; Al Marzouqi, 2011).

Migrant population data, on the other hand, was extracted from estimates of migrant stock compiled by the United Nations Population Division (UNPD) (UNPD, 2019a) bringing together national statistical data from 232 countries and non-state geographic areas. In some cases, the country of origin data was recoded by the UNPD to account for geotagging that was not country specific – either due to it being based on a region larger than a single country, or a geographic area that was smaller than a country. Population data that did not include place of birth identifiers was also recoded by the UNPD using citizenship data to identify foreign citizens who were then enumerated as migrants (UNPD, 2019b). The resultant migrant population data represents the most accurate global estimate of migrant stock available.

Table 1: National prevalence of FGM/C in country-of-origin

Country of origin	Prevalence	Source
Benin	9.2%	MICS 2014
Burkina Faso	75.8%	DHS 2010
Cameroon	1.4%	DHS 2004
Central African Republic	21.6%	MICS 2018-19
Chad	28.9%	MICS 2019
Cote d'Ivoire	36.7%	MICS 2016
Djibouti	93.1%	EDIM 2006-07
Egypt	87.2%	EHIS 2015
Eritrea	83.0%	EPHS 2010
Ethiopia	65.2%	DHS 2016
Gambia	72.6%	DHS 2019-20
Ghana	2.4%	MICS 2017-18
Guinea	94.5%	DHS 2018
Guinea-Bissau	52.1%	MICS 2018-19
Indonesia	49.2%	RISKEDAS 2013
Iraq	7.4%	MICS 2018
Kenya	21.0%	DHS 2014
Kuwait	38.0%	Calculated by author
Liberia	38.2%	DHS 2019-20
Malaysia	60.1%	Calculated by author
Maldives	13.0%	DHS 2016-17
Mali	88.6%	DHS 2018
Mauritania	63.9%	DHS 2019-21
Niger	2.0%	EDSN-MICS 2012
Nigeria	19.5%	DHS 2018
Saudi Arabia	12.8%	Calculated by author

Senegal	25.2%	DHS 2019
Sierra Leone	83.0%	DHS 2019
Somalia	99.2%	SHDS 2020
Sudan	86.6%	MICS 2014
Tanzania	10.0%	DHS 2015-16
Togo	3.1%	MICS 2017
Uganda	0.3%	DHS 2016
United Arab Emirates	51.9%	Calculated by author
Yemen	18.5%	NHDS 2013
Zambia	0.7%	ZSBS 2009

Legend: Author calculated prevalence rated based on the following smaller studies: Kuwait (Chibber, El-saleh and Harmi, 2011), Malaysia (Ainslie, 2015; Dahlui, 2012; Ibrahim and Tegal, 2019; Isa et al., 1999; Khan, 2010; Marranci, 2015; Merli, 2010; Rashid and Iguchi, 2019), Saudi Arabia (Milaat et al., 2018; Rouzi et al., 2019), United Arab Emirates (Al Awar et al., 2020; Al Marzouqi, 2011).

5. Findings

Globally, the female migrant population was estimated at just over 130-million (UNPD, 2019a), while applying a simplistic Extrapolation of FGM/C Countries' Prevalence Data methodology to the data it was calculated that over 7.3-million of those migrants were potentially impacted by FGM/C (Table 2).

Table 2: Global potentially impacted migrant population by continent

Region of residence	Estimated migrant population impacted by FGM/C	Percentage of global total
Africa	3,029,986	41.3%
Middle East	1,856,901	25.3%
Asia	888,840	12.1%
Europe	830,427	11.3%
North America	574,030	7.8%
Oceania	147,975	2.0%
Latin America	4,052	0.1%

It is evident from this analysis that the country of residence of impacted migrant population skews heavily towards Africa, the Middle East and Asia, where FGM/C is already known to be practised by indigenous populations. However, a more granular look at countries of residence suggested that significant populations were to be found in countries not generally associated with the practice of FGM/C (Table 3).

Table 3: Global potentially impacted migrant population by country of residence

Country of residence	Estimated migrant population impacted by FGM/C	Percentage of global total	Known indigenous practice of FGM/C
Côte d'Ivoire	758,642	10.3%	Yes
Saudi Arabia	721,090	9.8%	Small-scale studies
United States of America	461,069	6.3%	No
United Arab Emirates	426,749	5.8%	Small-scale studies
Singapore	367,587	5.0%	No
Ethiopia	344,552	4.7%	Yes
South Sudan	262,825	3.6%	No
United Kingdom	242,941	3.3%	No
Kenya	236,389	3.2%	Yes
Kuwait	229,614	3.1%	Small-scale studies

It was evident from this initial analysis that the United States was home to one of the largest potentially impacted migrant populations globally, with only Cote d'Ivoire and Saudi Arabia boasting a larger migrant population potentially affected by FGM/C. This scoping analysis also suggested that over half of the potentially impacted female migrants' resident in the United States originated from three countries: Egypt, Ethiopia, and Somalia, while other significant populations originated from Nigeria, Indonesia, and Sudan.

6. Discussion

Further analysis of migration patterns within and between Africa, the Middle East, and Asia revealed a vital nuance that must be considered when applying the Extrapolation of FGM/C Countries' Prevalence Data method to areas where the practice is almost exclusively found within the migrant population, such as in Europe and the United States, namely, the potential for onward migration to these destination countries by children born to migrants resident in third countries. This calls for a more profound analysis of ethnic and ancestral

origins than simply considering a migrant’s country of birth, as is often the case, when assessing risk.

6.1 Migrant populations in Africa

This analysis shows that 41.5% of the global impacted migrant population migrated within Africa, while distribution of the migrant population across Africa suggests that most live within host countries with their own indigenous practising populations (Table 4).

Table 4: Top ten African host countries by size of the potentially impacted migrant population

Host Country	Total female migrant population in host country	Migrant population potentially impacted by FGM/C	Estimated FGM/C prevalence rate in migrant population	National prevalence rate in host country
Côte d'Ivoire	1,137,566	758,408	66.7%	36.7%
Ethiopia	615,120	344,552	56.0%	65.2%
South Sudan	423,875	263,061	62.1%	< 1.0%
Kenya	522,533	236,389	45.2%	21.0%
Chad	275,896	180,401	65.4%	38.4%
Sudan	615,941	131,722	21.4%	86.6%
Burkina Faso	376,508	126,476	33.6%	75.8%
Nigeria	567,087	99,300	17.5%	18.4%
Mali	230,802	89,195	38.6%	88.6%
Senegal	129,243	65,301	50.5%	23.3%

Significant disparities between host country prevalence rates and those within the migrant population were noted in several African countries. Since most impacted migrants within Africa originated from four countries of origin, these being Somalia, Sudan, Burkina Faso, and Mali, (each of which has exceptionally high FGM/C prevalence rates of 99.2%, 86.6%, 75.8% and 88.6% respectively), this inter-African migration needs particular

consideration when analysing data concerning migrants in Europe and the United States onward migration from third countries. The impact of this consideration seems obvious; children born to a Rwandese diplomat or humanitarian worker posted to the African Union in Addis Ababa would record their place of birth as Ethiopia. Likewise, a child born to a Somali refugee resident in the Dadaab refugee camp would record their country of birth as Kenya. In the first case, the child would incorrectly be considered at risk of FGM/C based on their place of birth, while in the second case, the child would be regarded as significantly less at risk than her ethnic ancestry might suggest.

6.2 Migrant populations in the Middle East and Asia

Likewise, this analysis showed that 25.3% of the global impacted migrant population migrated to the Middle East, the majority to the Gulf States (Table 5), while 12.1% migrated internally within Asia (Table 6).

Table 5: Top five Middle Eastern host countries by size of the potentially impacted migrant population

Host Country	Total female migrant population in host country	Migrant population potentially impacted by FGM/C	Estimated FGM/C prevalence rate in migrant population	National prevalence rate in host country
Saudi Arabia	4,121,156	721,090	17.5%	-
UAE	2,261,236	426,852	18.9%	-
Kuwait	1,021,042	229,646	22.5%	-
Yemen	183,214	151,055	82.4%	19.0%
Oman	374,700	54,897	14.7%	-

Table 6: Top four Asian host countries by size of the potentially impacted migrant population

Host Country	Total female migrant population in host country	Migrant population potentially impacted by FGM/C	Estimated FGM/C prevalence rate in migrant population	National prevalence rate in host country
Singapore	1,205,461	367,587	30.5%	-
Malaysia	1,333,221	225,649	16.9%	60.1%
Bangladesh	1,061,320	139,117	13.1%	-
Hong Kong	1,798,925	89,301	5.0%	-

Only one of the nine countries-of-residence in Asia and the Middle East (Yemen) has a documented indigenous practising community evidenced by a national representative survey (DHS1997, DHS2013). On the other hand, numerous small-scale studies have documented indigenous FGM/C in Malaysia (Ainslie, 2015; Dahlui, 2012; Isa et al., 1999; Khan, 2010; Rashid and Iguchi, 2019) and in each the Middle Eastern host countries with sizeable impacted migrant populations: Saudi Arabia (Milaat et al., 2018; Rouzi et al., 2019), United Arab Emirates (Al Awar et al., 2020; Al Marzouqi, 2011), Oman (Al Hinai, 2014; Thabet and Al-Kharousi, 2019), and Kuwait (Chibber, El-saleh and Harmi, 2011). This is in contrast to the intra-Asian migration context where almost all migrants originated from Malaysia (49.6%) and Indonesia (49.2%), and were shown to be resident in Singapore, Bangladesh and Hong Kong communities which are not known for indigenous practicing communities. This clearly necessitates the need to privilege ethnic ancestry over place of birth, to account for risk – for example, to Malay children who were born in Singapore and now reside in Germany.

Significantly, almost half of the potentially affected migrants in the Middle East are Egyptian (45.2%), with other notable countries of origin including Indonesia (24.2%), Sudan (11.5%) and Somalia (7.4%). Once again, these countries of origin have relatively high

prevalence rates (87.2%, 49.2%, 86.6%, and 99.2%, respectively), suggesting that this inward migration into the Middle East needs to be considered in the light of potential onward migration to Europe and the United States.

7. Limitations

These findings are limited by the fact that the available population data was not segmented by age. In those contexts where FGM/C prevalence rates fall over time, this potentially resulted in an overestimation of the prevalence in the younger population and a corresponding underestimation of prevalence in the older population. The results thus assume a normal distribution within the migrant population which is unlikely.

8. Future research

This analysis of migration patterns within and between Africa, the Middle East, and Asia suggests the need for specific migrant-focused interventions in far more countries than is currently the practice. Evidence would suggest that while some efforts are being made across Africa, for example, to address issues affecting Somali migrants resident in Kenya, much less is being done in this regard in the Middle East and Asia, which lack both robust prevalence data and government commitment to addressing the practice within the migrant population. There is a need to expand the scope of FGM/C prevalence estimation beyond the current dichotomy of indigenous populations of the global south and migrant populations resident in the global north.

9. Conclusions

While this analysis confirmed the need for research into FGM/C in the United States based on its ranking as one of the largest potentially impacted migrant populations globally, the research clearly indicates that much more attention needs to be focused on how one assigns risk to migrant populations based on ethnic ancestry rather than place of birth. This would enable data gathering which would account for the scale of intra- and inter-Africa, -Asia, and -Middle East migration and the potential for onward migration of those born in third countries.

This paper also calls for a focus on establishing the prevalence of FGM/C within migrant populations outside of the global north context especially in countries like South Sudan and Singapore that are not known to have indigenous populations that practice FGM/C.

References

28 Too Many, 2021. 28 Too Many | Research & Resources [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.28toomany.org/research-resources/> (accessed 10.5.21).

Ainslie, M., 2015. The 2009 Malaysian Female Circumcision Fatwa: State Ownership of Islam and the Current Impasse. *Womens Stud. Int. Forum* 52, 1–9.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2015.06.015>

Al Awar, S., Al-Jefout, M., Osman, N., Balayah, Z., Al Kindi, N., Ucenic, T., 2020. Prevalence, Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Female Genital Mutilation and Cutting (fgm/C) Among United Arab Emirates Population. *BMC Womens Health* 20, 79.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12905-020-00949-z>

Al Hinai, H., 2014. Female Genital Mutilation in the Sultanate of Oman.

Al Marzouqi, W., 2011. Fatal Traditions: Female Circumcision in the UAE. *Desert Dawn* 6–9.

Chibber, R., El-saleh, E., Harmi, J.E., 2011. Female Circumcision: Obstetrical and Psychological Sequelae Continues Unabated in the 21st Century. *J. Matern. Fetal Neonatal Med.* 24, 833–836. <https://doi.org/10.3109/14767058.2010.531318>

Dahlui, M., 2012. The Practice of Female Circumcision in Malaysia, in: *Archive.Is. Universiti Sains Malaysia (USM), Pulau Pinang.*

De Schrijver, L., Van Baelen, L., Van Eekert, N., Leye, E., 2020. Towards a Better Estimation of Prevalence of Female Genital Mutilation in the European Union: A Situation Analysis. *Reprod. Health* 17, 105. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12978-020-00947-2>

EIGE, ICF Consulting Ltd, 2018. *Estimation of Girls at Risk of Female Genital Mutilation in the European Union: Step-by-Step Guide, 2nd Edition.* European Institute for Gender Equality.

Equality Now, End FGM European Network, End FGM/C US Network, 2020. *Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting: A Call for a Global Response.*

Goldberg, H., Stupp, P., Okoroh, E., Besera, G., Goodman, D., Danel, I., 2016. Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting in the United States: Updated Estimates of Women and Girls at Risk. *Public Health Rep. Wash. DC* 131, 340–347. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003335491613100218>

Home Office, UK Government, 2015. *Mandatory Reporting of Female Genital Mutilation - Procedural Information.*

Ibrahim, Z., Tegal, E., 2019. *Towards Understanding Female Genital Cutting in Sri Lanka.* The Family Planning Association of Sri Lanka, Colombo, Sri Lanka.

Isa, A.R., Shuib, R., Othman, M.S., 1999. The Practice of Female Circumcision Among Muslims in Kelantan, Malaysia. *Reprod. Health Matters* 7, 137–144. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-8080\(99\)90125-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0968-8080(99)90125-8)

Khan, A., 2010. The Practice of Female Genital Mutilation Among The Rural Malays In North Malaysia. *Internet J. Third World Med.* 9.

Malik, Y., Rowland, A., Gerry, F., Phipps, F.M., 2018. Mandatory Reporting of Female Genital Mutilation in Children in the UK. *Br. J. Midwifery* 26, 377–386. <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjom.2018.26.6.377>

Marranci, G., 2015. Female Circumcision in Multicultural Singapore: The Hidden Cut. *Aust. J. Anthropol.* 26, 276–292. <https://doi.org/10.1111/taja.12070>

Merli, C., 2010. Male and Female Genital Cutting Among Southern Thailand's Muslims: Rituals, Biomedical Practice and Local Discourses. *Cult. Health Sex.* 12, 725–738. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691051003683109>

Milaat, W.A., Ibrahim, N.K., Albar, H.M., 2018. Reproductive Health Profile and Circumcision of Females in the Hali Semi-Urban Region, Saudi Arabia: A Community-Based Cross-Sectional Survey. *Ann. Saudi Med.* 38, 81–89. <https://doi.org/10.5144/0256-4947.2018.81>

Rashid, A., Iguchi, Y., 2019. Female Genital Cutting in Malaysia: A Mixed-Methods Study. *BMJ Open* 9, e025078. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-025078>

Rouzi, A.A., Berg, R.C., Alamoudi, R., Alzaban, F., Sehlo, M., 2019. Survey on Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *BMJ Open* 9, e024684. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2018-024684>

Thabet, H., Al-Kharousi, A., 2019. *Female Genital Mutilation in the Middle East: Placing Oman on the Map*, 1st edition. ed. National and University Library of Iceland.

UNICEF, 2022. *Towards Ending Harmful Practices in Africa: A Statistical Overview of Child Marriage and Female Genital Mutilation*. United Nations Children's Fund, New York.

UNICEF, 2016. *Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting: A Global Concern*. United Nations Children's Fund, New York.

UNICEF, 2014. *Female Genital Mutilation/Cutting: What Might the Future Hold?* United Nations Children's Fund, New York.

UNPD, 2019a. *International Migrant Stock 2019*.

UNPD, 2019b. *International Migrant Stock 2019 Documentation*.

WHO, 2020. *Female Genital Mutilation [WWW Document]*. URL <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/female-genital-mutilation> (accessed 10.5.21).